

Correlation of Magnetic Resonance Imaging Staging (MRI) with International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) Staging of Carcinoma of Cervix: An Observational Diagnostic Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Carcinoma Cervix, a prevalent malignancy in young women, necessitates early detection and accurate staging for effective management. This study explores the correlation between Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) staging and International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) staging for Carcinoma of Cervix.

Aims/Objectives: To study the correlation between MRI staging and FIGO staging in Carcinoma of Cervix. To assess the utility of MRI in evaluation of primary invasive carcinoma with respect to location, size, local extent and staging.

Study Design: Cross-sectional observational.

Results: 60 females were participants in the study with 45% falling in the 41-50 years range. Parity and HPV infection were identified as prominent risk factors. The most prevalent stage of the disease in the study was stage IIA. Staging comparison between clinical examination and MRI revealed varying degrees of correlation across FIGO stages. Interrelated agreement using Kappa statistics was calculated to check for agreement between clinical staging and MRI staging. Kappa value was found to be 0.656 indicating moderate agreement between two investigations.

Conclusion: MRI is proven to be more sensitive and specific in detecting early disease as well as early tumour invasion to adjacent structures. MR findings help in early detection and accurate staging of the disease which ultimately help the clinician to tailor the treatment suited for individual patient.

Keywords: Carcinoma of Cervix, FIGO Staging, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Tumor Staging, Gynecological Cancer.

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Introduction

Carcinoma Cervix is a common malignancy presenting in younger women of childbearing age group and pre-menopausal women with an average onset at the age of 45 years. Its management depends completely on early detection and staging, therefore, an accurate pre-treatment staging of Carcinoma of Cervix is of utmost importance.

The most common pre-disposing factor of cervical cancer is the infection of cervical epithelium by human papilloma virus (HPV), few types of which (HPV 16 and 18) are known to have a high oncogenic potential. The overall prevalence of cervical HPV infections is 5%–20%. Other risk factors include high parity, smoking cigarettes, long-term use of oral contraceptives, and exposure to diethylstilbestrol (DES) in utero and high number of sexual partners. The age distribution of invasive cervical cancer is bimodal, showing a first

peak between age group 35 and 45 years and a second peak between 60 and 64 years. The mean age of onset is 52 years, however, the disease tends to have an earlier onset. Cervical carcinoma usually presents as vaginal bleeding, unusual vaginal discharge, pelvic pain, dyspareunia and post coital bleeding. It is important to detect the disease early in its course, and further staging it correctly in order to facilitate appropriate treatment.

MRI is generally not the initial investigation for diagnosis cervical cancer but is recommended for assessment of tumor characterization and local extension in patients with histologically proven cervical cancer. MRI provides valuable pre-treatment information that aids in deciding the mode of treatment particularly surgery and/or radiotherapy. It is the investigation of choice for tumor staging: assessing the depth and extent of

infiltration. MRI has proven to be the most accurate imaging modality (90%) for distinguishing between tumors confined to the cervix from tumor with parametrial infiltration (stage IB from IIB). The staging of cervical cancer is most important, particularly for distinguishing between early disease (stages I and IIA) that can be treated with surgery alone from advanced disease (stage IIB or greater) that must be treated with radiation with or without chemotherapy. MRI has proven its accuracy for evaluation of tumor size, usually within 0.5 cm of the surgical size, in 70–90% of cases. MRI is also useful in the evaluation of distant lymph node metastases.

The commonly used International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) staging is based on clinical evaluation, and is subject to errors when compared to surgical staging. Clinical staging shows an error of 20-25% depending on the stage of the disease. Cross-sectional imaging viz. computer tomography (CT) and Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are the modality of choice for staging of Carcinoma of Cervix. Out of these two, MRI is superior because of its excellent soft tissue resolution, lack of ionizing radiation and hence can be performed as and when required.

Aims and Objectives

- To study the correlation between MRI staging and FIGO staging in
- Carcinoma of Cervix.
- To assess the utility of MRI in evaluation of primary invasive carcinoma with respect to location, size, local extent and staging.

Methodology

Type of Study: Observational Diagnostic study (Prospective).

Period of Study: 1 year.

Equipment: All MRI were done on 1.5T MRI machine.

Method of Collection of Data:

All patients referred to the department of Radio diagnosis with clinically suspected cases of carcinoma of cervix in a period of 1 years were subjected for the study.

A written informed consent was obtained before performing an MRI scan. FIGO staging done using clinical evaluation and investigations like hysteroscopy, cystoscopy, proctoscopy, IVU, X-ray of chest and skeleton were correlated.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Clinically suspected cases of Carcinoma of cervix.
- Newly detected cases of Carcinoma Cervix confirmed by HPE.
- Suspected cases of recurrences following treatment.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patient having history of claustrophobia.
- Patient having history of metallic implants insertion, cardiac pacemakers, aneurysm clips, retinal implants & metallic foreign body in situ.

Results and Observations:

Table 1: Age distribution in study subjects

Age (Years)	Frequency	Percentage
31-40	18	30.0
41-50	27	45.0
51-60	9	15.0
>60	6	10.0
Total	60	100.0

Table 2: Risk factors in study subjects

	Risk factor	No. of subjects	Percentage
Parity	2	6	10.0
	3	19	31.7
	4	21	35.0
	5	10	16.7
	6	4	6.7
	HPV infection	4	6.7
	Smoking	4	6.7

Table 3: MRI findings in study subjects

MRI Findings		No. of subjects	Percentage
Bulky cervix		42	70.0
Location of lesion	Only anterior wall	6	10
	Only posterior wall	14	23.3
	Both	34	56.7
	None	6	10
Growth pattern	Endophytic	13	21.7
	Exophytic	41	68.3
Size (cm)	<4	15	25.0
	>4	39	65.0
	No	6	10.0
Uterus involvement		46	76.7
Vaginal involvement	Upper two-third	34	56.7
	Lower one-third	10	16.7
Parametrial involvement		26	43.3
Ureteral involvement		8	13.3
Hydronephrosis		8	13.3
Bladder involvement		6	10.0
Rectal involvement		7	11.7
Lymph node involvement	Regional	6	10.0
	Distant	6	10.0
Distant organ involvement		1	1.7
Endometrial collection		24	40.0

Table 4: Staging in clinical as well as MRI examination

FIGO Stage	Clinical examination		MRI		Percent
	No. of subjects	Percent	No. of subjects		
IA	2	3.3			
IB	12	20.0	8		13.3
IIA	14	23.3	20		33.3
IIB	9	15.0	9		15.0
III	9	15.0	8		13.3
IV	8	13.3	9		15.0
None	6	10.0	6		10.0
Total	60	100	Total		60

Table 5: MRI staging in comparison to Clinical staging

Clinical (FIGO) stage		MRI staging			Total
		Lower	Correlated	Higher	
Clinical (FIGO) stage	I A	0	0	2	2
	I B	0	5	7	12
	II A	1	11	2	14
	II B	3	6	0	9
	III	0	8	1	9
	IV	0	8	0	8
	None	0	6	0	6

Table 6: Interrelated agreement using Kappa statistics

		Value	Asymp. Std. Error ^a	Approx. T ^{o b}	Approx. Sig.
Measure of Agreement	Kappa	.656	.071	11.438	.000
N of Valid Cases		60			

Kappa value was found to be 0.656 indicating moderate agreement between two investigations.

Stage IB1 in a 45 year old patient:

Figure 1: (a) T2 Sagittal; (b) T2 Axial

Figure 1 shows bulky cervix with an ill- defined mass in the posterior lip of cervix (limited to the cervix). Mild free fluid is noted in the endometrium.

Stage IB2 cervical carcinoma in 43 year old patient:

Figure 2: (a) T2 Sagittal; (b) T2 Axial

Figure 2 shows a well-defined hyperintense lesion limited to the cervix with mild free fluid in the endometrium.

Stage IIA1 cervical carcinoma in a 50 year old patient:

Figure 3: (a) T2 Sagittal; (b) T2 Axial

Figure 3 depicts an ill-defined hyperintense lobulated lesion in the cervix extending inferiorly upto proximal vagina.

Stage IIA2 cervical carcinoma in a 44 year old patient:

Figure 4: (a) T2 Axial; (b) T2 Sagittal

Figure 4 illustrates a large ill-defined lobulated mass lesion in the cervix, extending superiorly to the body of uterus and inferiorly up to proximal vagina.

Stage IIB cervical cancer in 48 year old patient:

Figure 5: (a) T2 Sagittal; (b) T2 Coronal; (c) T2 Axial

Figure 5 demonstrates an ill-defined hyperintense lobulated mass lesion in the endocervical region involving the lower uterine segment and upper 1/3rd of vagina. Laterally, it is extending into the parametrium with parametrial fat stranding and disruption of hypointense ring.

Stage IIIB cervical cancer in a 55 year old patient:

Figure 6: (a) T2 Sagittal; (b) T2 Coronal; (c) T2 Axial; (d) T2 Coronal

Figure 6 shows a large ill-defined mixed intensity lesion involving the cervix, part of the body of uterus and proximal one third of the vagina with parametrial invasion bilaterally. The lesion is invading bilateral distal ureters leading to hydronephrosis.

Stage IVA cervical cancer in a 36 year old patient:

Figure 7: (a) T2 Axial; (b) T2 FRFSE FAT-SAT Axial; (c) T2 Sagittal

Figure 7 shows tumor extending into the posterior wall of the urinary bladder, consistent with bladder invasion. Multiple flow voids are noted within gall bladder suggestive of Cholelithiasis.

Stage IVB cervical cancer in a 50 year old patient:

Figure 8: (a) T2 Sagittal; (b) STIR Coronal; (c) T2 Axial; (d) T2 Sagittal

Figure 8 demonstrates an ill-defined cervical mass with loss of fat planes with the urinary bladder. Axial T2WI, Sagittal T2WI and Coronal STIR images show multiple solid cystic lesions in sacrum and left iliac blade suggestive of Metastasis. Lesion is invading the parametrium and left ureter causing hydronephrosis and hydro-ureter.

Discussion

Cervical cancer is the principal cause of death amongst women in the developing world. More than 80% of women with newly diagnosed cervical cancer are living in developing countries; most of which are diagnosed with advanced disease.

The International Federation of Gynaecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) staging system updated in 2009 is commonly used for treatment planning but is

inadequate in evaluation of prognostic factors like tumor volume and nodal status. MRI gives us important information regarding the exact shape, volume, and direction of the primary lesion, local extent of the disease as well as the nodal status helping clinician to plan the treatment. Tumor behaviour towards chemo-radiation is also better evaluated with the use of MRI.

Clinical and ultrasound findings must be supplemented by MRI in all cases suspicious of cervical carcinoma. MRI is proven to be more sensitive and specific in detecting early disease (Stage IB onwards) as well as early tumor invasion to adjacent structures. T2W and DWI sequences were found to be most useful in detection of tumor invasion. MR imaging shows high sensitivity and specificity in depicting vital prognostic factors and,

whenever available, is recommended in adjunct to clinical examination. The MR findings of cervical carcinoma should be included in a multidisciplinary setting and discussed among the clinical and histologic findings of each patient, an effective approach that provides accurate staging and risk stratification and allows for individualized medical and/ or surgical treatment. MR findings help in early detection and accurate staging of the disease which ultimately help the clinician to tailor the treatment suited for individual patient. To conclude, MRI should be the investigation of choice in cases suspected with cervical malignancy.

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